

Explained in 60 Seconds

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Fulldome

Fulldome videos are primarily science documentaries that are projected onto a domed surface, typically in a planetarium. Many full-dome videos deal with astronomy, but other subjects are also appropriate, especially those relating to topics or environments

that are difficult or impossible to experience, such as being deep underwater, inside the human body or in the future. We like to think of a flat-screen video as a window into another world, but with a fulldome video you can poke your head up inside that

world and become immersed within it; think of a 3D animated movie crossed with IMAX and put it in a planetarium.

Figure 1. Audiences are immersed in another world in a fulldome theatre.
Credit: Morehead Planetarium and Science Center

